

YARN-SCALE ANALYSIS OF NOVEL TEXTILE COMPOSITES LACKING AN ELEMENTARY REPRESENTATIVE ELEMENT

Yann M. Le Cahain¹, Dmitry S. Ivanov¹

¹Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol, UK.
Queen's Building, University Walk, Bristol BS8 1TR, United Kingdom
Email: yann.lecahain@bristol.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/composites/>

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ABSTRACT

Composites architectures evolve and become increasingly complex due to the growing capabilities of manufacturing technologies and sophisticated material designs aimed at optimising load flow, mitigating against damage development, functionalization, etc. Tow steering methods, textile technologies, and advanced draping techniques result in highly-curved fibre paths and complex interlacing of yarns/tows at sub-component level requiring efficient computational approaches to the analysis of stress distribution at the yarn scale. This study demonstrates an example of such novel manufacturing technique.

The method presents 3D printing of a reactive liquid resin into a dry textile reinforcement, followed by consolidation and subsequent resin infusion. The purpose of the print is to stabilise preforms prior to impregnation and functionalise the material. Printing results in a number of interesting structural features: thickness variation in a predefined pattern, local patches with distinctly different properties, fibre-bridged interfaces between printed and infused resin. These features significantly extend the tool box available to manipulate composite properties and, at the same time, reveal a need in a new design philosophy.

The paper discusses mechanical response of these materials and a new numerical approach to assess stress at the yarn scale. Tensile tests, accompanied by optical surface strain measurements, are carried out to explore the material. A pragmatic modelling approach is proposed to overcome the lack of representative volume and understand the influence of complex structural features on composite performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern composite manufacturing techniques have now achieved a level where the composite properties can be designed through sophisticated positioning and orienting of its elements: yarns, tows, plies, interleaves, resin pockets. Laminates with curved tows tailored for optimised buckling and strength performance can be obtained using Embroidery, Tow Steering or Automatic Fibre Placement techniques. Textile technologies are used to create structurally integral net-shaped preform for component with high through thickness performance. Novel techniques for drape, lay-up, and integration of functional elements are constantly developed to broaden design possibilities.

In order to evaluate mechanical performance of these complex structures it is desirable to carry out stress and damage analysis at the yarn/tow scale. It is particularly important for the design stage when making decisions on multiple settings of manufacturing parameters. However, this becomes increasingly difficult due to intrinsically complex topology of the internal composite architectures.

This study explores an architecture created by a novel manufacturing technique which provides a characteristic challenge for design and stress analysis. The liquid print method [1] introduces a pattern of cured consolidated patches in a dry multi-ply preform. The patches play a role of stiff skeleton which integrates individual plies and controls preform geometry and thickness in critical component locations (edges, corners, joints, etc.). Due to the preliminary consolidation, the preform remains unaffected by subsequent draping, bagging and resin infusion processes. This ensures a better dimensional stability, the mitigation against various processing defects and yarn path control. The process of creating a patch is implemented as a 3D printing of liquid reactive resins through a series of

high precision injections. Every injection builds a layer of liquid resin at a predefined position through the preform thickness. Multiple injections implemented in a predefined step provide a uniformly impregnated patch spanning through preform thickness. Once the patches are printed the preform is consolidated and cured locally (patch by patch) or all at once under pressure and temperature corresponding to the curing requirements of a printed resin.

The print process may have significant implications on the material response:

- 1) Resin used for patches can differ from the resin used for the subsequent infusion. The printed resin can be functionalised, toughened or stiffened by incorporating a wide range of additives or choosing a reactive system with different mechanical and physical properties.
- 2) Due to their locality, the patches may be consolidated at higher pressure than imposed by the vacuum bag in the Resin Infusion under Flexible Tooling (RIFT) process. This may or may not create a local thickness and fibre volume fraction (V_f) variation depending on ply lay-up and pressure difference. The variation of up to 20% difference [1] can be achieved if over 6-7 bar pressure is used for patches in an orthogonal woven laminate.
- 3) 3D printing allows integrating the printed patches in any predefined pattern. The patch size can also be chosen by adjusting the volume of injected resin. When a regular pattern of patches is printed over the preform surface, a new material scale is created.
- 4) The interface between the printed and infused patches provides an interesting feature. On the one hand, the chemical bond at the interface is weaker implying that the transfer of through-thickness shear stress may be affected. On the other hand, the interfaces are bridged by fibres insuring continuous load transfer across the patch boundaries.

The role of these features in deformation and failure accumulation process needs to be understood. The manufacturing scheme provides a lot of new governing parameters that can be used to manipulate and tune the mechanical response of a component: patch properties, patch interface properties, patch pattern, patch sizes, thickness/ V_f variation, etc. The current study undertakes an effort to (a) understand the deformation mechanisms through direct experimental observations (manufactured samples are tested in tension with in-situ surface strain measurement), (b) develop a simulation tool that would be able to handle the analysis of load flow at the yarn scale in a rational pragmatic manner.

The classical approach to stress analysis [2] is to consider an elementary building block of a composite – Representative Volume Element (RVE). The yarn and component scales can then be separated through an assumption of the periodic stress fields. This concept is applicable to micro-architectures with stochastic distribution of elements, in which case RVE has to be large enough to include sufficient number of structural elements but small compared to the component dimensions, and for regular textiles, where the building block is naturally defined as the unit repeat of a preform. Modern structures are often lacking an RVE or have an RVE size comparable to the dimensions of a component. Moreover, many manufacturing processes such as draping or non-uniform compaction due to bagging add complex component-scale features to even initially regular structures. The printing process presents a characteristic case where manufacturing technique violates the textile periodicity by imposing an additional length scale through thickness variation, extra yarn crimp, and patch interfaces.

There exist various approaches to reduce computational expenses in the analysis of geometrically complex material architectures. An interesting class of approaches is a volume decomposition, where a computationally heavy problem is solved in parts. The main challenge then is to organise a data exchange between the separated volumes to represent their interaction correctly. In Domain Decomposition [3, 4] the sub-problems were linked through Boundary Conditions (BC) in an iterative procedure. Chinesta et al. [5-7] used specially constructed shape functions to solve the problems with a lower dimensionality. A different decomposition approach designed for textile laminates was proposed in [8-10]. It was based on reconstructing the displacement field on boundaries of individual plies and then setting the obtained functions as BC.

In this paper, a variation of this concept was adopted for the analysis of the printed architectures. The individual plies of a laminate with macro features (thickness variation) were considered in isolation from the laminate. The boundary conditions imitating the ply interactions were derived from

a boundary value problem set on a shell approximation of the laminate. The provided scheme allowed to reduce the computational time substantially. The accuracy and potential of this approach are discussed in the paper.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Manufacturing process

Tensile specimens were manufactured using a two-step manufacturing technique. In the first step, the reactive liquid resin was printed into a dry multi-ply textile laminate followed by curing and consolidation in a hot press to create cured patches. In the second step the material was infused using a variant of a vacuum assisted infusion. The print process was realised by means of a novel rig built by modifying the RepRap Mendel 3D printer [1] where a thermoplastic extruder was substituted by a syringe holder (standard medical 10 ml syringes could be fitted, 21G needles with a diameter of 0.8 mm were used). The printer has three translational degrees of freedom to move the syringe's needle and an independent controller enabling the injection of the specified amount of resin at a required speed and quantity. The rig implements programmed injections in any position both in-plane and through-thickness of a preform.

Carbon woven 5-harness satin fabric was used as the reinforcement (Hexcel G0803/G0963, with an areal density of 285 g.m⁻² per ply, 3K yarns and a yarn spacing of 1.43 mm). 90*300 mm preforms were formed by laying up 18 plies in the same direction. Two 250*19.3 mm tensile specimens could be obtained from each of them. In the first step, three rows of an epoxy resin (Gurit Ampreg 22 with a viscosity of 722 cP at 20°C) were printed at a distance of 40 mm across the specimen length – Figure 1. Each row was formed from merging 8 individual patches (pins) and each pin was made of 18 injections through thickness (one per ply) of 6 µl volume at a speed of 4 ml.min⁻¹. The resin was degassed during 20 minutes before being placed in the syringe. The entire injection process took approximately one hour. The resin pins were cured under a press applying 6 bar pressure and 75°C temperature during 5 hours. The obtained rows were of approximately 10 mm width.

Figure 1: Top view of tensile specimens

In order to test feasibility of local injection process, the second (liquid moulding) stage was conducted in the spirit of additive manufacture. The conventional RIFT process was substituted by a novel procedure where the resin was delivered locally. Similar to the 3D printing, the resin was injected using syringes. However, this time the injections were vacuum assisted and applied through a vacuum bag (manually). This aimed at limiting complexity of RIFT, reducing the amount of consumables (no resin distribution mesh was needed), providing a better surface finish, and ensuring a better flow control. A reusable silicon sheet was placed on top of the preform to avoid losing the vacuum during the injection process. Finally, the composite was cured in an oven at 75°C during 5 hours with a pump on to keep a good level of vacuum through the entire curing procedure. Glass fibre end tabs were glued after the sample manufacture – Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 2: Edge view of tensile specimen with thickness variation

2.2 Specimen features

Specimens obtained in this process exhibited peculiar features. There was a pronounced thickness variation between the printed zones which were consolidated at a high pressure level. Cured patches had a minimum thickness of 4.6 mm whereas thick regions, which were consolidated in the vacuum bag, had a thickness 20% higher. The bottom surface, which was in contact with the tool, was flat while the top surface was curved. In the current settings of the print process the capillary forces were dominant in the viscous flow. The flow non-uniformity resulted in a micro porosity. The volume fraction of the micro-pores could be estimated to be below 2.5% [1]. Few larger isolated pores with a characteristic size of 0.2 mm could be found in the central infused area and even larger macro pores with a characteristic size of 1.4 mm were found in the grip (infused) region.

Micrographs in Figure 3 did not reveal any obvious interface between the printed and infused regions. During the second stage of the manufacturing process, manual injections were performed starting from one end (grip region) of the sample and going to another end – 14 injections points in total. Thus, the resin flow was controlled by the injections locations and order. However, no effect of the resin flow orientation could be seen on the micrographs.

Figure 3: Micrograph of a manufactured specimen showing internal structure, thickness variation and impregnation defects

3 TENSILE TESTS

The tensile tests were performed on a 100 kN Instron hydraulic machine. La Vision 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system was used to assess the difference in strain distribution due to the variation in thickness and fibre volume fraction and measure the applied strain field calculated as an average strain over the sample surface. The field view covered the area of ~ 270 pixels (19.3 mm) along the sample width and ~ 1600 pixels (115 mm) along the length (flat sample side was examined). The characteristic speckle size was around 0.5 mm. The displacement was determined on the subset size of 31 pixels and the step between the subset was chosen to be 8 pixels.

The samples exhibited a linear elastic response up to 0.7-0.8% of applied strain at which point they failed in the grips. The surface strain field at the moment preceding the failure is shown for one specimen on Figure 4. A clear difference between the deformation in thin (printed) and thick (infused) zones was seen. The average tensile strain in the loading direction differed by 25% in the selected regions, reaching over 0.94% in the infused area. The variation in local strain at the yarn scale was even higher. This level of strain far exceeds the characteristic strain at damage onset in woven composites (0.2-0.6%). Hence, a considerable level of micro cracking in the transverse yarns was expected. However, no detectable damage could be seen either on the front/back surfaces or on the polished cross-sections after examining the loaded samples. Additionally, no delamination or any damage at the patch boundaries was detected. The explanation for this phenomena is yet to be found

and a detailed yarn-scale model is required to understand the deformation mechanisms in this material.

Figure 4: DIC tensile strain field before failure of one specimen

4 MODELLING APPROACH

There are two scales of fibre waviness and thickness variation: in the unit cell the waviness is due to yarn interlacing and the manufacturing technique imposes a pattern at the sample (macro) scale. An Elementary Building Block (EBB) at the sample scale covers a half wavelength of thickness variation and contains at least 3 unit cells in the length direction, 3 unit cells in the width direction, and 18 unit cells through thickness – Figure 5 (there are three rows of consolidated patches, 6 EBB in each sample). Taking into account the complexity of each unit cell, the model becomes unrealistically large for stress analysis, particularly when it is needed for design purposes.

The study is focused on exploring the feasibility of a pragmatic stress analysis by means of a form of the domain decomposition. In line with [8-10], it was attempted to construct BC that could be set on an isolated ply and reproduce the deformation of this ply within thick multi-ply curved laminate. The BC were derived from an auxiliary boundary value problem which was set on a 2D shell representation of the laminate. As will be shown further, such model can correctly reproduce deformed shape of the laminate but is unable to capture yarn stress distribution. Hence, an additional step is required to assess deformation patterns within a ply.

The proposed scheme was tested on a hypothetical two-ply laminate with a characteristic thickness variation. A smaller model was considered in order for the reference problem to be small enough. Two plies in a reference problem were not intended to reproduce the deformation in the actual 18-ply laminate discussed previously but for the validation of the approach. However, it sets a realistic validation case for the modelling approach without submitting to enormous computational expenses.

Figure 5: Elementary Building Block used in the model

4.1 Model of a ply in the printed laminate

The solid and finite element models of the deformed ply in a curved laminate were generated with the following algorithm:

1) The geometrical model of a flat single ply preform is created using the WiseTex software developed in the University of Leuven [11]. It takes as an input the basic fabric properties, such as pattern, yarn spacing, yarn dimension, etc., and generates the model where every yarn is approximated by a set of cross-sections of a constant shape but varying dimensions. Each cross-section is positioned along yarn midline and is described by the coordinate of its centre, three orientation vectors, and two dimension parameters: thickness and width.

2) The model is read by the Python script written for the finite element environment of Abaqus software. The model discretises every cross-section by placing a set of points along the cross-section contours. The points are grouped so that the pair for every point is placed symmetrically relative to the major axes of the cross-section. Every point is then checked to be outside of any other yarn in the unit cell since the assumption of constant shape cross-section may lead to a certain yarn interpenetration. If the yarn overlap is detected, the point pair is moved along the line connecting the pairs to get rid of the interpenetrations [12].

3) A geometrical transformation is applied to every point of each cross-section of every yarn to distort the unit cell in correspondence with the macro-scale deformation. This transformation, given by equation (1) and shown on Figure 6, is continuous. It reflects the thickness variation and the change in curvature. The orientation vectors for every yarn cross-section are also redefined to set the correct stiffness properties.

4) Once the geometry is defined. The solid model is built in Abaqus by constructing cross-sections and then lofting (extruding) the solid volume through each one of them. All the elements in the volume connected by the cross-sections, called segments, are assumed to have the same fibre orientation. The unit cells of adjacent plies are assembled together in the reference problem or remain separated in the case of decomposition. The obtained model realistically represents the yarn architecture but cannot be practically meshed by the conventional elements due to intrinsically complex and irregular geometry of the inter-yarn space.

5) The voxel meshing is adopted where the considered volume is discretised into a number of regular elements of equal dimensions. The properties of these elements and fibre orientations are assigned based on the position of the element centre. Figure 7 shows a sketch of an exaggerated deformation of unit cell with an increase in thickness of 60%.

Figure 6: Exaggerated deformation of a single unit cell of a ply experiencing a change in thickness and curvature

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \bar{x} \\ y &= \bar{y} \\ z &= \underbrace{\bar{z} \left(1 + \bar{x} * \frac{t}{L} \right)}_{\text{Thickening part}} + \underbrace{f(\bar{x})}_{\text{Curvature change part}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ and (x, y, z) are the coordinates of a material point before and after the consolidation deformations correspondingly: \bar{x} , x – along the warp direction, \bar{y} , y – along the weft direction, and \bar{z} , z through thickness, \bar{h} and h are the maximum thickness of the preform before and after the consolidation respectively. L is the length of the specimen, t is the percentage of increase in thickness

f is a Gompertz step-wise function changing from 0 at $x \rightarrow -\infty$ to +1 at $x \rightarrow +\infty$ (the span of the transition region is defined by the parameters of the function). This function conveniently describes the macro change in thickness of the unit cell between the infused and printed region. The parameters of these functions were defined using micrographs of the specimens. Along with the changes in the position of every point in the yarn cross-sections the orientation of each cross-section had to be redefined. The orientation vectors (step 3) were transformed in agreement with the geometrical transformation of (1):

$$V = R^{-1} \bar{V}$$

With V one of the orientation vectors and R the Jacobian matrix for the change of basis from the old to the new coordinate system:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{dx}{d\bar{x}} & \frac{dy}{d\bar{x}} & \frac{dz}{d\bar{x}} \\ \frac{dx}{d\bar{y}} & \frac{dy}{d\bar{y}} & \frac{dz}{d\bar{y}} \\ \frac{dx}{d\bar{z}} & \frac{dy}{d\bar{z}} & \frac{dz}{d\bar{z}} \end{pmatrix}$$

Equation (1) intrinsically increases fibre length by 2.6% which can be neglected at this stage. This was decided to simplify the modelling process but will be adjusted in future work.

Figure 7: Example of deformed unit cell (60% of increase in thickness)

4.2 The 2-ply model: implementation

The reference problem for the 2-ply model contains 18 unit cells. In a first approximation no edge effect is considered and hence, the laminate can be assumed infinite in the width direction. That allows considering one strip of the unit cell along the loading direction and reduce the model to 6 by imposing Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) in the transverse direction as mentioned in step 4 of the modelling process. Every yarn in a unit cell is composed of 45 segments.

The thickness increase is set to 20% in accordance to the micrograph – Figure 5. 0.8% of tensile strain is applied using symmetry BC. Chamis model [13] is used to define yarn linear elastic properties based on local V_f and fibre and matrix properties. The thickness variation implies that yarns will have a different V_f in thin and thick regions. Thus, yarn properties are defined for each voxel by scaling V_f in flat non-consolidated model proportionally to thickness evolution (the average intra-yarn V_f in fully consolidated/printed area is approximately 75% and in infused area is 63%). The voxel mesh is

composed of 75,000 quadratic 20-node brick elements with reduced integration (C3D20R) to avoid shear locking and hourglassing.

In addition to the 2-ply reference model, models of individual plies are constructed for the decomposition approach – (detailed in section 4.3). Each separate ply is modelled with a coarser mesh than the reference problem: 6,750 quadratic 20-node brick elements per ply, and has the same geometry than in the reference model. BC for isolated plies are derived from a shell approximation of the composites (details are below). The shell model is composed of 400 quadratic 8-node elements – S8R. Materials from the voxel mesh are defined on the shell model as a composite lay-up for each shell element. Thus, the mid-plane of the shell model is situated at the middle of the lay-up following the planar geometry defined in the xy plane whereas in the solid model it corresponds to an inclined plane which follows the deformation/thickening of the unit cells.

4.3 Decomposed approach

The partitioning of the laminate departs from an observation that local deflections of each ply in a laminate are the same for all plies. In this study it was attempted to derive these deflections from a 2D problem. This problem was constructed by creating a shell model with a composite lay-up roughly representing yarn geometry. Figure 8 illustrates with a 2D example the shell implementation where every row of voxel elements taken through laminate thickness is transformed into a single laminate shell element. Every voxel element then represents a single ply in the shell composite lay-up.

Figure 8: Illustration of the shell 1D representation of a 2D geometry using a composite lay-up

The shell model discards the out of plane shear and breaks the continuity of the load flow with its composite lay-up material definition. Thus the stresses obtained in the correspondent boundary value problem are not to be trusted. However, the shell model provides an approximation of the deflection and can be used to define BC for the higher resolution solid model.

Once the 2D problem is solved, out of plane deflection is imposed at the outer surfaces of each ply as BC. The in-plane deformation of the ply is enforced using identical BC in both the 2-ply reference and 1-ply decomposed problems: symmetry BC imposing the tensile strain (set on the two external surfaces perpendicular to the tensile direction) and PBC in the transverse direction as it is assumed here that there is no edge effect. A linear interpolation of the deformation shape is performed to define node displacements as the shell and solid meshes do not necessarily match. The interpolation is performed with the Python function `griddata` from Scipy library.

5 MODELLING RESULTS

The laminate deflection shapes obtained in full voxel and 2D shell formulation are compared on Figure 9. The shape of curve obtained in 2D formulation is well captured but absolute values are not perfectly matched. As known from [9] the distribution of out-of plane shear stresses has a significant

influence on the deflection shape. The intensity of shear stresses is determined by the presence of outer surface and number of plies in the composites. The laminate shell model cannot capture through-thickness shear distribution correctly and hence the results are supposed to differ but be roughly proportional. An appropriate energy scaling procedure [8, 9] can be applied to approach the exact deflection shape. In this study, the obtained deflection was adopted for BC as is without any further tuning to assess the quality of a first order approximation.

Figure 9: Representative out of plane deformation of the textile specimen

After the problems were solved, the stresses were locally averaged over the segment volumes in order to suppress mesh sensitivity caused by the rough discretisation. On Figure 10, the stress in the fibre direction (local coordinate system) is shown for a warp yarn aligned with the loading.

The macro trend of tensile stresses is captured despite a coarser mesh used for the decomposed plies compared to the 2-ply reference model. Local variations of stresses are not reproduced precisely but such accuracy may be acceptable at a design stage. It is expected that a further refining of the model and energy scaling of the BC may be applied in order to improve the precision of the estimate. However, this study goes beyond the scope of the current paper.

Figure 10: Longitudinal stresses within one yarn (highlighted above) along fibre direction and averaged on each segment

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study showed an example of a structure obtained with a novel manufacturing method which exhibited peculiar features: thickness variation, internal boundaries, non-periodic pattern of the reinforcement, etc. These features are characteristic for a two stage consolidation process but can also be observed in more conventional manufacturing where non-uniform consolidation and draping deformation create local heterogeneities at the component scale. In the new print process, aimed at functionalization and local stabilisation of the preform, these features can play a role in development or suppression of damage mechanisms.

Tensile tests were performed on specimens manufactured with the novel technique to study their mechanical response. The effect of thickness variation was successfully captured showing higher strain in thicker infused regions. The specimens failed in the grips which prevents any conclusion concerning the strength. Moreover, unusually high strain before damage onset was discovered but this observation still needs a further investigation.

To understand composite deformation mechanisms and to optimise the novel process, a new modelling technique was considered. The approach presents a scheme where full 3D models of individual plies in a laminate were coupled with a 2D representation of the structure. The 2D model allowed to capture overall deformation pattern and a 3D model of a ply was used to get higher resolution of stress. This permitted to reduce computational efforts substantially compared to the computation of the entire laminate. It was found that the macro trend of tensile stresses can be captured. Such an approach still needs to be refined – using an energy scaling of the BC – but is a first step towards a detailed stress analysis of a representative model composed of 18 plies.

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